

From farm to Europe: addressing the challenges of scaling carbon schemes

D2.2

**Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to
achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.**

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Executive Summary

Purpose

This deliverable contributes to the **CREDIBLE** project's overarching goal of fostering trust and momentum for carbon farming in the European Union. Specifically, it addresses the **issue of scaling carbon certification schemes from farm to national and EU levels**. The report presents the findings of Focus Group 2.2, which was tasked with exploring the optimal scale of governance for a robust and viable carbon certification framework in Europe. It aims to inform the development and implementation of the **Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF)** regulation by providing stakeholder-driven recommendations on governance, methodologies, certification processes, or registry design.

Intended audience

This document is intended for **policymakers** at EU and national levels, particularly those involved in climate action, agricultural policy, and environmental governance. It is also relevant to certification bodies, project developers, researchers in climate and land-use sciences, and land managers engaged in carbon farming across agricultural, forestry, and wetland sectors. The insights and recommendations herein are designed to **support decision-making processes** related to the design and implementation of carbon certification schemes under the CRCF.

Description of the main activities

Focus Group 2.2 was coordinated by **AC3A** and **I4CE** and brought together a diverse range of stakeholders, including public institutions, NGOs, researchers, and private actors: project developers, existing standard representatives, auditors, MRV providers. The group conducted a series of consultations between September 2023 and July 2025. The methodology combined qualitative and quantitative approaches. Initial discussions explored experiences with existing schemes such as the French Label Bas-Carbone¹. Then, a survey was designed to assess preferences and risks associated with different governance scales. The survey targeted carbon certification and carbon farming experts. The results were analysed alongside findings from another European project called VERTA² and debated in multi-actor settings. This iterative process ensured that the

¹ The Label Bas-Carbone ('low carbon label') is the first voluntary climate certification framework in France, allowing to certify greenhouse gas emission reduction and carbon sequestration projects in all sectors (forestry, agriculture, transport, construction, etc.)

² VERTA is a EU project laying out suggestions on the implementation rules and the registry of the CRCF.

recommendations were grounded in practical experience and reflective of diverse perspectives across Europe.

Key results

Result 1: The various certification governance options involve different **transaction costs**, which should be better assessed when designing the CRCF. This is a major issue because there is a risk that a significant share of **transition funding could be diverted** to these transaction costs.

This issue is discussed in the context of debates on **monitoring** (e.g. the level of monitoring accuracy with the number of indicators collected or the tool used: model vs. direct measurement vs. remote sensing) and less in terms of the appropriate level of centralisation. A **more decentralised approach**—particularly regarding methodology—allows for local history and specificities to be taken into account and fosters bottom-up innovation. However, the **more decentralised the approach**, the higher the transaction costs.

Result 2: Experience with existing carbon certification standards shows that economic operators often **exploit loopholes in methodologies** and comparing the adequacy of different methodologies and tools is challenging. A **model/tool validation step** is therefore needed to ensure compliance with the methodology. **Independent consultants and researchers** should play a key role in reviewing the entire process and evaluating whether the assigned objectives have been achieved—beyond the work of auditors. This role should not be underestimated by the Commission.

Research and practice implications

It would be useful to **evaluate the transaction costs** associated with the different CRCF governance scenarios in order to guide the selection of the most appropriate option. These costs should include fees for consultants and researchers responsible for reviewing methodologies and proposed MRV tools, as well as expenses for auditors—which can increase significantly in highly decentralised scenarios.

Clarifying the governance process could also help **existing standards** identify ways of becoming part of the CRCF, for example as certification schemes.

Policy implications

DG CLIMA should ensure that the CRCF remains **sufficiently centralised** to provide harmonised rules across the EU while still **taking local contexts** into account. It should also **assess the associated transaction costs**, which tend to increase with the level of flexibility granted to stakeholders. In addition, it is crucial to allocate an **adequate budget to remunerate independent experts and consultants** for scrutinizing methodologies, conducting project checks, and overseeing certification bodies (auditors).

Conclusion

The analysis showed that there are several levels of governance for the different components of carbon certification (methodology, tools, auditing, project validation, registry). An assessment of the benefits and risks associated with these scenarios was carried out, and the findings suggest that **transaction costs** and the need to **limit loopholes** argue in favor of a **centralised framework**. However, **safeguards** have been proposed with a view to **adapting to local contexts** and **promoting innovation**.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

CF: Carbon Farming

CRCF: Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming

DG CLIMA: Directorate-General for Climate Action

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

FG: Focus Group

GA: Grant Agreement

GHG emission tools: Greenhouse gas emissions reduction calculators using models and parameters provided by methodologies and protocols.

Label Bas-Carbone: a voluntary climate certification framework in France, led by the Ministry for the Environment, certifying GHG emission reduction and carbon sequestration projects in all sectors (forestry, agriculture, transport, construction, etc.).

LULUCF: Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry

MRV tools: Monitoring-Reporting-Verification tools, interface integrating the certification rules defined in the methodology: additionality, quantification, permanence management tools, monitoring over time, audit reports, etc.

MS: Member State

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

SO: Specific Objective

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

VERTA: CRCF *VERification* Technical Assistance. The VERTA project has been conducted throughout 2024 to support the Commission to develop implementation rules for the verification of carbon removals under the CRCF and to start the process of scoping an EU-wide registry for carbon removals

WP: Work Package

Project summary

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded project under the topic HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-06, titled: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU (project acronym: CREDIBLE, Grant Agreement #101112951).

The main goal of the CREDIBLE project is to build momentum and trust for the implementation of carbon farming in the EU. This has been primarily achieved by setting up and moderating a network of initiatives/projects/stakeholders for favouring transparency, environmental integrity, and methodology standardisation in soil carbon accounting. Such a network is responsible for pushing forward multiple discussions (articulated around three main themes: which practices; what standards; how to monitor) and is expected to evolve from a mostly technical/scientific network at the onset of the project, into a process catalysing policy making and business innovation toward its end. The transparent, open access, multi actor dialogues required to build trust and co-create solutions is orchestrated around three annual European Carbon Farming Summits, which present opportunities for the network to interact with the broader stakeholder community and grow to the point it would attract further fundings for long term sustainability. Through the action, four specific objectives (SO) are achieved:

SO1) to build and disseminate a practical toolbox for promoting carbon farming, capable of taking into account local land uses, best practices, and multi-actor interests;

SO2) to identify options for benchmarking and selecting standards, certification mechanisms, and policy instruments for carbon farming;

SO3) to favour the establishment of a network of soil carbon data collectors and repositories to improve measuring and monitoring carbon dynamics;

SO4) to build up processes and tools to drive conversations for the upscaling of carbon farming. CREDIBLE's ambition is to support the European Commission and the Expert Group on Carbon Removal in the identification and upscale of solutions for soil carbon farming. Tables 1 and 2 provide further information on the structure and composition of the project.

Table 1 - CREDIBLE's work package structure.

WP#	WP Name	Lead
WP1	Practical knowledge and fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development	11-BSAG
WP2	Navigating and selecting carbon standards and policy instruments	12-EEB
WP3	Existing monitoring capabilities as enablers of soil data collection and sharing	8 - UFZ
WP4	Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU	15-CKIC
WP5	Project management and coordination	1 – SAE

Table 2 - CREDIBLE's consortium composition.

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras SL	SAE	ES
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	UCSC	IT
European Conservation Agriculture Federation	ECAF	BE
Association des Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique	AC3A	FR
Greifswald University	UG	DE
Ecologic Institute	ECO	DE
European Association of Remote Sensing Companies	EARSC	BE
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH - UFZ	UFZ	DE
Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals	CreAF	ES
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España U de coop sociedad cooperativa	COOP	ES
Baltic sea action group	BSAG	FI
European Environmental Bureau	EEB	BE
European agroforestry federation	EURAF	FR
BioEconomy Cluster	BEC	SK
Climate KIC Foundation	CKIC	NL
University of Helsinki	UH	FI
Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	ILVO	BE
Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	CREA	IT
Agricultural Applications Private Company (AgroApps)	APPS	GR
Institute for Climate Economics	I4CE	FR
Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - DIMITRA	ELGO	GR

Introduction

The **Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming** (CRCF) Regulation targets several possible sources of funding (for instance voluntary and compliance markets, public subsidies).

Private standards at the global scale, such as Verra or Gold Standard, have been operating for years in Europe. Public national standards such as the Label Bas Carbone in France or MoorFutures in Germany have been developed more recently and others are in development.

A **centralised** European carbon farming certification framework aims to **provide clarity** for farmers and financiers in a context where private and public carbon certification schemes are multiplying at European level, to reduce transaction costs (MRV, auditing and other certification costs) and to ensure the same level of requirements for everyone. Conversely, a **decentralised approach** can be better tailored to local circumstances and easier to use for local operators.

In the framework of the CREDIBLE project, the **focus group** “2.2” was set up by AC3A and I4CE to question the optimal scale of governance for robust and viable schemes. Learnings from stakeholders involved in international, national, and local certification frameworks, helped reveal the strengths and weaknesses of the **different scales** of governance (EU level, Member States level, existing standards or local level) and predict potential interaction of overlapping schemes at different levels, bottlenecks and barriers.

Through **consultations of experts** involved in the certification of carbon credits in agriculture, forestry and peatlands (project developers, existing standards, auditors, etc.), this focus group supported the development of **recommendations** to better shape the governance of the future Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Framework (CRCF).

Towards an optimal scale of governance for robust and viable schemes

1. Context: developing regulatory framework

Regulation (EU) 2024/3012³, adopted in December 2024, establishes a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products, and provides elements for the future governance of the CRCF. However, further clarification of the processes and the roles of the various actors is still needed. In June 2025, the European Commission launched a public consultation on an **implementing act**⁴ describing certification processes and defining the scope of the EU-wide registry⁵. The first **carbon farming methodologies** are also expected to be published in early 2026 through delegated acts.

The illustration below shows the governance model proposed by the EC at the beginning of 2025. We have highlighted (in red) several issues requiring clarification, such as:

- The role of MS, which may extend beyond accrediting certification bodies.
- The role of certification schemes in defining rules that are not part of the EU-wide methodologies.

Figure 1. A summary diagram of the certification processes under the CRCF and the associated issues (source: I4CE).

³ [Regulation \(EU\) 2024/3012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products](#)

⁴ [Verification of carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products \(implementing rules\)](#)

⁵ [VERTA project. Final report on Scoping of the CRCF registry and minimum requirements for certification scheme registries, February 2025.](#)

The work carried out by the focus group 2.2 of the CREDIBLE project had to be regularly adjusted in light of to the latest developments from DG CLIMA and the expert group on Carbon Removals⁶ set up by the European Commission.

As the **governance structure and timetable** of the CRCF gradually became clearer, the issues raised with the panel of experts within the focus group needed to be looked at differently and readjusted. For some questions, the level of governance had already been decided or clarified between the preparation of the survey and its dissemination at EU level. For example: a European registry will be operational in 2028 and until then (2025-2028), the registries of the certification schemes will be used. Therefore, the recommendations should aim to **mitigate the potential negative effects** of this decision.

For other questions, adjustments still needed to be made or clarified. For instance: while the methodologies are being developed by the Commission, some details on how operators should apply them are left to the different certification schemes. In such cases, the recommendations can **help shape or clarify governance**.

2. Challenges tackled by the Focus Group 2.2

Focus Group 2.2 was established within the Horizon Europe CREDIBLE project to assess the **implications of different governance levels** for carbon certification, by analysing the strengths and limitations of both **centralised and decentralised** approaches.

At the outset, two main possible evolutions for existing standards were identified:

- **Integration into the CRCF:** Existing standards would operate solely as certification schemes under the CRCF framework.
- **Coexistence:** Existing standards would continue to operate independently, using their own methodologies and tools alongside the European framework.

To explore these options, the group analysed the risks and benefits of different theoretical governance scenarios-ranging from most centralised to most decentralised-under the future European framework, across key certification components: methodology, validation, GHG assessment tools, auditor accreditation, certificates, and registry management.

⁶<https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&groupID=3861>

To inform this analysis, the group conducted:

- Expert workshops and consultations
- An online survey
- Debate sessions at the European Carbon Farming Summits in Valencia (2024) and Dublin (2025)

The resulting **recommendations** aim to support the effective implementation of the CRCF regulation, ensuring a certification system that is rigorous, fair, transparent, and adaptable to local realities.

3. Governance of the Focus Group 2.2

Focus Group 2.2 was set up within the Credible Project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme and was coordinated by the [Association of Chambers of Agriculture of the Atlantic Area \(AC3A\)](#) and the [Institute for Climate Economics \(I4CE\)](#). It brought together a wide range of **European stakeholders involved in carbon certification**: project developers, certification bodies, representatives of existing standards, researchers, NGOs, public and private institutions.

Contributors included:

The Agriculture and Food Climate Club, the Forest and Wood Climate Club, the French Ministry for Ecological Transition, Energy, Climate and Risk Prevention, the French Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty, the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine Ireland, OECD, PEFC International, Verra, IUCN UK Peatland Programme, European Landowners Organization, European Environmental Bureau, The Norwegian Forest Owners' Federation, Royal Forestry Society of Belgium, St1 Nordic Oy, INRAE, Idele - French Livestock Institute, Oklima, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH - UFZ, University of Galway, ASPECT Unit, ART-ER, Land Life Iberia, Bax, EIT Climate KIC, Coopérative Carbone La Rochelle, Skog, Baltic Sea Action Group, Wetland Products Foundation, Moy Park Beef Orléans, SCARA, Kybernos ESG Data Services GmbH, Regenagri, Agricarbon, TÜV Nord, GAEC des Belles Filles, All'i'homme, Symbiose Normandie, SOLENAT, ACCLENA.

4. Methodology to collect insight

September 2023

Initial discussion with associations involved in Payments for Ecosystem Services (Symbiose, Alli'homme, Acclena, etc.) to gather feedback on the French Label. Bas-Carbone.

Objective: Identify strengths and weaknesses of the national Label to inform recommendations for the future European framework.

September 2023 to April 2024

Development of a questionnaire on the optimal scale of governance for each component of the CRCF (methodologies, tools, project validation, auditor accreditation, registry), in collaboration with I4CE.

Objective: Prepare a structured consultation tool to collect expert opinions across Europe.

January to March 2024 – Preparation for the EU Carbon Farming Summit:

Internal meetings with FG members to organize sessions and discussions for the Summit.

Objective: Structure public exchanges around governance scenarios for carbon certification.

7 March 2024 - Panel discussion at the EU Carbon Farming Summit:

Roundtable with representatives of existing schemes and governance levels (Verra, LandLife, Label Bas-Carbone, Irish Government, etc.).

Objective: Discuss the added value and challenges of a European certification framework in relation to existing standards.

7 March 2024 Participatory workshop at the Summit:

Workshop with 70 participants divided into groups to debate four governance scenarios (EU-level, Member States, international standards, regional standards).

Objective: Identify benefits and risks of each scenario for the future CRCF.

March 2024

Consolidation of key messages from the panel and workshop discussions.

Objective: Recommendations to be submitted to the European Commission.

April 2024 – Online workshop by I4CE with Climate Clubs:

Exchange on CRCF governance, roles of private actors, Member States, and the EU, and the future of the Label Bas-Carbone.

Objective: Gather sectoral expert insights on centralization and coordination challenges.

May to October 2024 – Survey dissemination:

Online survey completed by 23 experts from 13 countries on governance preferences and risks.

Objective: Identify consensus areas, tensions, and paths forward for CRCF governance.

February 2025 – Cross-analysis of survey results:

Integration of survey findings with conclusions from the VERTA⁷ project.

Objective: Refine recommendations using the latest technical and policy insights.

10 February 2025

Session with FG members to validate and finalize policy recommendations.

Objective: Prepare contributions for the EU Carbon Farming Summit in Dublin.

March 2025 – Presentation at the EU Carbon Farming Summit in Dublin:

Public presentation of FG 2.2's recommendations.

Objective: Influence the development of the CRCF with stakeholder-informed proposals.

June – July 2025 – Feedback on the CRCF draft implementing regulation:

FG 2.2 contributed to a collective feedback note analyzing the EC draft regulation.

Objective: Provide concrete recommendations on governance, methodologies, MRV tools, project validation, and registry design.

July - September 2025 - Final deliverable from the FG

Objective: assess the implications of different levels of governance (European, national, local) for carbon certification, by analysing the strengths and limitations of centralised and decentralised approaches and providing concrete recommendations

Main outcomes from the Focus Group

1. Stakeholder Perspectives on Certification Governance

This section presents the main findings and recommendations of Focus Group 2.2 for **each key component** of the carbon certification framework. To explore these questions, the group analysed the **risks and benefits** of three theoretical governance scenarios under the future European framework, across key certification components:

⁷ This VERTA project has been conducted throughout 2024 to support the Commission to develop implementing rules for the verification of carbon removals under the CRCF and to start the process of scoping an EU-wide registry for carbon removals. https://climate.ec.europa.eu/document/download/45708194-a447-46c7-8f81-cc96d621b490_en?filename=event_20250205_crcf_registry_rules_report_en.pdf

- Methodology development and validation,
- GHG assessment tools,
- Project validation,
- Auditors' accreditation
- and registry management.

The three scenarios (from most centralised to most decentralised) are:

Scenario A | European Level

A highly centralised model where most certification components are developed and approved at EU level. Common methodologies, tools, and a single registry are used across Europe. Existing standards may either act as validators under EU methodologies or compete with the European framework on overlapping scopes (e.g. carbon sequestration, N₂O emission reductions).

Scenario B | National Level

Member States play a central role. Methodologies, project validation, auditor accreditation, and registry management are delegated to national authorities. This mirrors the current French Label Bas Carbone (LBC) model, which would need to evolve to align with CRCF rules. Other Member States would also need to engage similarly.

Scenario C | Existing Standards

A decentralised model where eligible public or private standards manage certification components. This resembles the CORSIA framework, which recognises standards that meet its criteria under an umbrella system.

These scenarios represent extreme models, and hybrid approaches combining elements from each scenario across different certification components are also possible.

The survey collected answers from 23 respondents representing 11 different EU Member States, and 2 from outside the EU.

The majority of respondents were involved in carbon certification schemes, mainly as:

- Entity managing a certification scheme
- Intermediary between project holders and funders
- Project developer
- Methodology developer

Type of organisations	
Other	1
Corporation	2
Private non-profit organisation	3
Public entity / Government body	2
Research Institute / University	4
Small and medium Enterprise	4
NGO/ Civil society	7

Scale of the organisation	
Local	2
International	5
European	6
National	10

Methodology development and validation

Methodologies set baselines, additionality and GHG accounting rules, making their governance critical for consistency and cost-efficiency across the EU. The survey asked respondents to rate the viability of three governance options (EU, national, existing standards) for developing and validating methodologies, select their preferred option (see figure on the right), and explain their choice.

Scenarios considered and feedback from respondents

Scenario A - EU level

European methodologies are developed by the EC, with possible input from a panel of European experts, and adopted through delegated acts; their validation is also carried out by the EC, potentially following European public consultation.

Feedback: A single EU methodology ensures strong comparability and economies of scale, but reaching consensus can be time-consuming.

Scenario B - National level

The EC publishes overarching methodologies for each sector, which are then adapted by public or private entities in each MS to reflect territorial specificities; these adjusted methodologies are validated by national authorities to ensure compliance with EU rules.

Feedback: National adaptation enables innovation and responsiveness, yet risks fragmentation and unequal capacities across Member States.

Scenario C – Existing standards

The Commission provides global methodological guidelines, while existing public or private standards adjust their methodologies accordingly; validation is performed by these standards, subject to compliance with EU requirements and, where relevant, national consultations.

Feedback: Leveraging existing methodologies accelerates deployment (shorter validation time, methodologies already existing) but does not resolve credibility issues or method proliferation.

Implications for the CRCF

According to the CRCF Regulation, methodologies will be developed by the European Commission, which aligns with the survey results showing a clear preference among respondents for public-sector leadership in both the development and validation of methodologies.

FG 2.2 Recommendations

1. Define precise EU-level rules within CRCF methodologies to avoid leaving room for interpretation by project developers in order to ensure consistency. These rules should establish the **broadest possible common base**, covering baseline scenarios, additionality tests, and GHG monitoring requirements (emission factors, equations, models, etc.). The more prescriptive the methodology, the **lower the transaction costs** (e.g., for project development and auditing).
2. Allow controlled flexibility through specific protocols proposed by certification schemes, under strict conditions:
 - The developer must demonstrate the added value of the proposed protocol compared to the EU-defined methodology.
 - Member States must be involved to ensure credibility, robustness, independence, and alignment with national regulations.
 - Protocols from different schemes operating in the same Member State must meet equivalent requirements to prevent “forum shopping”, namely operators exploiting the system by choosing the most favourable scheme.
 - All protocols must be validated by the European Commission, based on technical expert advice.
 - Methodology developers may go beyond EU rules by introducing additional criteria where relevant.
3. As UNFCCC LULUCF reporting methodology differs among Member States, enable them to refine methodologies by using models or emission factors from their LULUCF reporting, provided these parameters are at least as stringent as CRCF requirements, to ensure consistency across regulations.
4. Establish regular review cycles for methodologies to keep them aligned with scientific progress, involving independent researchers, consultants, and technical experts.
5. Include an MRV cost estimate for each methodology to ensure that high accuracy does not lead to disproportionate costs, which could divert funding away from the transition.

GHG assessment tools and models

GHG assessment tools operationalise methodologies and directly affect comparability, costs, and user uptake. The survey asked respondents to rate the viability of governance options for developing, validating, and approving tools/models (EU, national, existing standards), select their preferred option (see figure on the right), and explain their choice.

Scenarios considered and feedback from respondents

Scenario A – EU level (option 1)

A single public EU tool, available in multiple languages, is used across the Union.

Feedback: This offers economies of scale, but updating and sustaining a free tool is challenging given the diversity of existing tools already in use by advisors.

Scenario A – EU level (option 2)

Multiple tools (public or private) can coexist; the EC approves tools that comply with EU methodological specifications.

Feedback: This model balances consistency and innovation, but requires adequate resources and time for the approval process.

Scenario B – National level

Multiple tools coexist; Member States approve tools that comply with the methodological specifications

Feedback: Encourages innovation and local fit, giving room for improvement, yet risks disparities and uneven capacity across countries.

Scenario C – Existing standards

Multiple tools coexist; Standards approve the tools used within their scope.

Feedback: Already operational in many contexts, but carries a risk of inconsistent outputs across tools and schemes.

Implications for the CRCF

The survey indicates that a unique EU tool is not seen as credible, yet any tool should be EC-approved to ensure equity and comparability. Respondents also favour describing the role and expected behaviour of tools/models directly within EU methodologies.

FG 2.2 Recommendations

1. Validate tools through the EC based on technical expert advice, benchmarking tests, and consultation with MS (especially for local tools).
2. Audit tools regularly to ensure they remain aligned with evolving methodologies and produce consistent outputs.
3. Specify within methodologies how tools/models must implement rules and parameters (e.g., equations, emission factors, boundary conditions).
4. Anticipate and budget tool costs (development, maintenance, approvals) to avoid bottlenecks and ensure long-term operability.

Project validation

Project validation confirms that a project complies with the referenced methodology and that the application is complete (checks performed by the competent authority or a verification body). Under the CRCF, it results in a certificate of compliance. Therefore, the survey asked respondents to rate the viability of three governance options (EU, national, existing standards) for this step, select their preferred option (see figure on the right), and explain their choice.

Scenarios considered and feedback from respondents

Scenario A – EU level

A European body (the Commission or an appointed agency) evaluates all project proposals in a single EU format (likely in English).

Feedback: Ensures uniformity but raises language barriers and risks limited local representation.

Scenario B – National level

A national body (ministry or national agency) evaluates proposals written in the national language and ensures compliance with EU rules.

Feedback: Proximity improves relevance and access, yet there may be longer timelines for validation process and divergent interpretations between MS.

Scenario C – Existing standards

Existing standards can evaluate projects submitted in their geographic areas⁸, ensuring compliance with European rules.

As there are possible overlaps between existing standards, in a given area, a project developer may have to choose to which standard to submit the project.

Feedback: Shorter validation times are possible thanks to experience and fee-funded capacity, but double validation can occur without a unique registry.

⁸ As for the verification step, the standards often do not carry out the validation themselves, but appoint independent auditors instead.

Implications for the CRCF

Survey results point out Member States as key players in project validation. While the CRCF foresees validation by certification bodies, Member States can work alongside schemes to adapt validation rules to their context.

FG 2.2 Recommendations

1. **Tighten rules** at methodology/protocol level to gain precision, reduce ambiguity, and lower validation costs.
2. **Specific baselines:** where standardised baselines cannot be implemented in the first years, developers will use project-specific baselines and must demonstrate baseline choice and additionality. This issue requires more scrutiny from certification bodies and the CRCF should set detailed requirements for establishing such baselines.
3. Member States could play a role here to define **parameters for additionality tests** or to provide a list of credible **specific scenarios** to guide certification bodies and ensure consistency within the country.

Auditors’ accreditation and registry

Auditors' accreditation and registry management are key to ensuring verification quality, transparency, and traceability under the CRCF, which defines certification bodies as auditors and requires robust governance to prevent double counting and ensure market integrity. In this context, the survey invited respondents to assess the viability of different governance scenarios for (i) auditor accreditation and (ii) registry management, indicate their preferred options (see figures below), and explain their reasoning.

Scenarios considered and feedback from respondents

Auditors’ accreditation

Scenario A – EU level

A single EU list of accredited auditors decided by the Commission.

Feedback: Creates economies of scale for EU-wide actors and avoids repeated national accreditations.

Scenario B – National level

National lists of accredited auditors.

Feedback: Lower entry barriers for smaller auditors operating in a single country.

Scenario C – Existing standards

Lists of accredited auditors decided by existing standards.

Author’s note: This scenario was not considered sufficiently viable by the participants

Registry

Scenario A – EU level

One single European registry; sub-EU verification bodies report directly or via linked registries.

Feedback: Simplifies access to the certificates for potential buyers, avoids double counting risks, and benefits from economies of scale.

Scenario B – National level

National registries managed by national bodies. Registries must follow technical specifications set by the European Commission.

Author's note: Although this scenario was considered viable by a significant number of respondents, they did not justify their choices.

Scenario C – Existing standards

One registry per certification standard. Registries must follow technical specifications set by the European Commission.

Feedback: Leverages already available registries.

Implications for the CRCF

Survey results confirm strong support for a **single EU registry** fully managed by the European Commission. For **auditors' accreditation**, respondents favour a role for national accreditation bodies, consistent with CRCF provisions.

FG 2.2 Recommendations

Adopt a **single EU registry**, fully managed by the European Commission. This would allow economies of scale, avoid risk of double credit allowance and double purchase by credit buyers and facilitate the purchase of carbon credits by trans-EU companies.

With regard to the **accreditation of auditors**, the survey responses are consistent with what is planned and therefore do not call for any recommendation.

According to the survey outcomes, Member States should play a role in auditors accreditation which is provided for in the CRCF with the implication of national accreditation bodies.

2. Towards a Shared Vision for CRCF Governance

Panel and Audience Reflections

During the [EU Carbon Farming Summit](#) held in Dublin in March 2025, AC3A and I4CE co-hosted a dedicated session focused on the governance of carbon certification under the future CRCF. This session included a panel discussion and an open exchange with the audience, during which the key findings of the stakeholder survey and the draft recommendations of the Focus Group (FG) were presented and debated.

The objective was to refine the policy recommendations one final time, based on collective insights and feedback from summit participants, and to move towards a **shared understanding and emerging consensus** within the carbon farming community on the governance challenges and opportunities ahead.

The panel featured diverse perspectives, including: a French farmer, a European certification body, a methodology developer from a technical Institute, and a representative from the European Commission.

The audience brought together a diverse panel of stakeholders (see figure below) from all over Europe to discuss the trade-offs between centralised and decentralised approaches.

Discussions highlighted the trade-offs between centralised and decentralised approaches, and the need to **balance harmonisation, operability, and local relevance**.

Key Challenges Identified

Prescriptive EU-wide methodologies were widely supported to reduce loopholes, lower transaction costs, and build trust among buyers and auditors. One certification body noted that prescriptive methodologies reduced validation time from two months to four days.

Preserving space for innovation and local adaptation was highlighted as essential, particularly for Member States. While harmonisation is necessary to ensure consistency and comparability, rigid frameworks risk overlooking territorial specificities and existing practices.

Variability in GHG assessment tools was flagged as a major credibility risk. Harmonisation and validation of tools were seen as essential, with the Climate Farm Demo project mentioned as a potential contributor.

Need for continuous review processes, involving both scientific experts and field-level stakeholders, to ensure methodologies evolve with practice and science.

Administrative burden for farmers remains a barrier. A farmer shared that despite implementing carbon-friendly practices and conducting impact assessments, they opted out of certification due to excessive complexity.

Preserving space for innovation and adaptation to local specificities remains a critical challenge, particularly for Member States. While harmonisation is necessary to ensure consistency and comparability, the framework must remain flexible enough to accommodate diverse agro-ecological contexts and foster bottom-up innovation.

Clarifying the requirements for model validation and the role of the European Commission is essential to ensure system credibility. A lack of clear procedures may hinder trust and coherence across Member States, both in the short term and as part of a long-term improvement strategy.

Recommendations from the Session

The following recommendations emerged from the panel and audience discussions:

Methodologies

Develop highly **prescriptive methodologies** at EU level to ensure consistency and reduce costs.

Allow **Member States to refine methodologies** using national LULUCF parameters, provided they meet CRCF standards.

Tools and Validation

Validate **GHG assessment tools through the European Commission**, with input from Member States and sufficient resources for technical review.

Promote group certification models to reduce administrative burden, especially for small or fragmented farms.

Governance and Support

Ensure a **robust and transparent review process** involving both scientific and field expertise.

Provide **clear governance pathways** and **sufficient funding** for independent experts and auditors.

Design the CRCF business model to **balance robustness with manageable transaction costs** and fair stakeholder remuneration.

Start with a **simplified framework and gradually increasing precision** over time was seen as a pragmatic approach.

Outputs from the Focus Group

The following section outlines the key outputs of Focus Group 2.2, developed through multi-actor engagement and expert consultation. For those wishing to explore the work further, detailed deliverables and supporting materials are available.

- Two **milestone reports** on the optimal scale of governance for carbon certification submitted to public consultation:
 - [*CREDIBLE project. The issue of scale for the carbon certification framework, March 2024.*](#)
 - [*CREDIBLE project. From single farms to nations: is there an optimal scale for robust and viable schemes? June 2025.*](#)
- Two **panel discussions and workshops** organised at the EU Carbon Farming summit to discuss the added value and challenges of a European certification framework in relation to existing standards.
- A **European-wide online survey** to question different scenarios of governance and identify their risks and benefits, and the work required to move forward on the points on which there is no consensus.
 - [*CREDIBLE project. Survey on the optimal scale of governance of the certification schemes under the CRCF. February 2025.*](#)
- A **collaborative feedback** from the FG 2.2 on the Draft Act Implementing Regulation on Carbon Removals Certification (CRCF)
 - [*CREDIBLE project. Feedback on the Draft Act Implementing Regulation on Carbon Removals Certification \(CRCF\), July 2025.*](#)
- The present report, **final deliverable** issued from all consultations carried out within the FG 2.2.

Final recommendations

The final recommendations presented below aim to consolidate the insights gathered throughout the Focus Group’s activities into actionable guidance. They reflect the overarching conclusions drawn from the analysis of governance scenarios, stakeholder consultations, and survey results, and are intended to support the coherent and effective implementation of the CRCF across Europe.

- The harmonisation of certification frameworks is a top priority. Experts surveyed **strongly support** the establishment of a European certification framework to unify existing schemes under a **single, high-quality standard**. This would reduce confusion, improve comparability, and build trust among stakeholders.

Cautionary note: Harmonisation must not lead to increased complexity or transaction costs. Without careful design, the proliferation of standards may paradoxically worsen fragmentation — as humorously illustrated below.

Source: xkcd.com/927 – A humorous reminder of the risks of multiplying standards in the name of simplification.

- **Transaction costs** must be carefully assessed and minimised. Different governance scenarios (centralised vs. decentralised) imply varying levels of cost for project validation, auditing, and methodology development. These costs can divert transition funding and discourage participation, especially among small-scale farmers.

- **Independent experts and consultants must be commissioned and adequately funded to assess the framework.** Their role is essential to ensure methodological integrity, validate tools, and oversee certification bodies. A centralised CRCF should enable economies of scale to support this.
- **Clarify the full certification process,** from methodology development to emission reduction validation. This includes defining the final governance scenario to provide **visibility for existing standards** and their potential integration into the CRCF.
- Design a **robust and viable CRCF business model**, including funding sources, transaction costs, and minimum viable project size. This will ensure long-term sustainability and accessibility for diverse stakeholders.
- **Anticipate the transition phase** between existing frameworks and the CRCF. Farmers already engaged in certification schemes need visibility and continuity — for example, through a transitional period during which existing credits are recognised under the CRCF.
- Ensure **continuous review and improvement of methodologies and tools**, involving both scientific experts and field-level stakeholders. This will help maintain credibility and adapt to evolving practices and technologies.
- Promote group certification models to **reduce administrative burden**, especially for fragmented or small-scale farms.

References

[CREDIBLE project. The issue of scale for the carbon certification framework, March 2024.](#)

[CREDIBLE project. Survey on the optimal scale of governance of the certification schemes under the CRCF. February 2025.](#)

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[VERTA project. Final report on Scoping of the CRCF registry and minimum requirements for certification scheme registries, February 2025.](#)

[VERTA project. Final report on Verification rules under the CRCF regulation.](#)

[Regulation \(EU\) 2024/3012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products.](#)

[Verification of carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products \(implementing rules\).](#)

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